

POSSIBLE ANTITUBERCULOUS COMPOUNDS. PART IX. PREPARATION OF BENZYLIDENE AND BENZYL DERIVATIVES OF 4-AMINODIPHENYLAMINE

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Twelve new substituted *N*-benzylidene and the corresponding *N*-benzyl derivatives of 4-aminodiphenylamine have been synthesised with a view to ascertaining the effect of basic strength on antituberculous activity.

The significance of primary aromatic amines in the chemotherapy of tuberculosis has been investigated by Kuroya (*J. Exper. Med.*, 1927, 7, 255), Erlenmeyer *et al.* (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1945, 28, 1406) and by Doub (*Amer. Rev. Tuberc.*, 1950, 61, 407) who noticed activity in 4-aminodiphenyl, its isosteres and β -naphthylamine.

The authors have reported herein the synthesis of a series of substituted *N*-benzylidene and *N*-benzyl derivatives of 4-aminodiphenylamine in order to obtain compounds of basic strength intermediate between those of a basic primary amine and diphenylamine-4-aryl-or-alkyl-amidines described earlier (*loc. cit.*).

Condensation of 4-aminodiphenylamine with piperonal, vanillin, cinnamaldehyde, β -naphthaldehyde, benzaldehyde, and *p*-methyl-, (*o*, *m* and *p*)-hydroxy-, *p*-propyl-, *p*-methoxy- and *p*-chloro- benzaldehydes furnished the expected Schiff's bases in good yields, ranging from 75 to 95%.

The latter were subsequently reduced catalytically to the corresponding benzylamino compounds. The completion of hydrogenation was confirmed by performing the dye test with the reduced product (found negative) and by finding out the mixed melting points.

The antitubercular activity of these compounds will be reported later on.

EXPERIMENTAL

(I). *N*-Benzylidene Derivatives of 4-Aminodiphenylamine.—These derivatives were obtained in good yields by refluxing an ethanolic solution containing equimolecular quantities of 4-aminodiphenylamine and freshly distilled substituted benzaldehydes for 30 minutes. The crystalline solids, which separated out on cooling, were filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. Properties of these are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

N-4-Substituted benzylidene-aminodiphenylamines.

S. No.	R=	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Calc.
1.	C ₆ H ₅	94-95°	85%	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₂	10.25	10.29
2.	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	115°	87	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂	10.02	9.79
3.	C ₆ H ₄ OH (o)	77-79°	85	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ O	9.91	9.72
4.	" (m)	128°	95	"	9.99	"
5.	" (p)	187-88°	88	"	9.50	"
6.	C ₆ H ₄ C ₂ H ₅ (p)	118°	88	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂	9.05	8.91
7.	C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ (p)	110-11°	85	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O	9.42	9.27
8.	C ₆ H ₄ Cl (o)	88°	91	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ Cl	9.05	9.10
9.	C ₆ H ₄ CH=CH	114-15°	75	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₂	8.88	9.39
10.	C ₆ H ₃ $\begin{cases} \text{OCH}_3 \text{ (m)} \\ \text{OH (p)} \end{cases}$	121-22°	78	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	8.63	8.80
11.	C ₆ H ₃ $\begin{cases} \text{O} \\ \text{O} \end{cases}$ CH ₂	96-98°	88	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	8.39	8.86
12.	C ₁₀ H ₇ (β)	145-46°	80	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂	8.33	8.69

(11). *N*-Benzyl Derivatives of 4-Aminodiphenylamine.—The Schiff's bases (0.5 g.), described above, and glacial acetic acid (30 c.c.) were taken in a hydrogenating bottle; Adams' catalyst (25 mg.) was added to it and the mixture was shaken in an atmosphere of hydrogen at a pressure of 60 lbs. per sq. inch for 5 to 6 hours. The solution was filtered, most of the solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure, and the residue neutralised with a strong ammonia solution. The solid so separated was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol or acetone (Table II).

TABLE II

N-4-Substituted benzylaminodiphenylamines.

No.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.
1.	60-61°	96%	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂	10.10	10.22
2.	84-86°	87	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂	10.20	9.72
3.	96-98°	85	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ O	9.70	9.65
4.	119°	98	"	9.12	"
5.	130°	.16	"	9.20	"
6.	54-56°	60	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂	8.69	8.86
7.	68°	50	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O	9.55	9.21
8.	78°	55	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ Cl	8.76	9.08
9.	60°	62	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₂	8.98	9.33
10.	133-35°	37	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	9.20	8.75
11.	83-84°	90	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	8.69	8.80
12.	154-55°	50	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂	8.27	8.64

Groups representing R correspond to those in Table I.

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